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Job Satisfaction as a Mediator in The Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Commitment Relationship: Evidence From The Manufacturing Sector in Jordan¹

Duygusal Zekâ ve Örgütsel Bağlılık İlişkisinde Aracı Olarak İş Memnuniyeti: Ürdün İmalat Sektöründen Elde Edilen Kanıtlar

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Abstract

The first aim of this article is to examine the effect of Emotional Intelligence (EI) on Organizational Commitment (OC), and the second aim is to understand whether Job Satisfaction (JS) has a mediating role in this relationship. The study was conducted with data obtained from different manufacturing companies in Jordan. The sample consists of 411 employees. The research was conducted with a quantitative method using reliable and valid scales to measure EI, JS and OC. Normality tests, descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis were performed on the obtained data using the SPSS program. In addition, the mediation test findings were confirmed using the SPSS PROCESS Macro application. According to the findings, EI has a significant and positive effect on both JS and OC. It was found that JS partially mediates the relationship between EI and OC. This finding shows that the positive effect of EI on OC works through increased JS. This result shows that employees with high emotional intelligence experience higher JS, which strengthens their commitment to the organization. The study supports the importance of EI and JS in promoting OC and contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence. The results

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emphasize the need for manufacturing companies to develop workplace policies that can enhance employees' EI and JS, so that companies can cultivate a more committed workforce.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Mediation Analysis, Manufacturing Sector

Özet

Bu makalenin ilk amacı Duygusal Zekânın (DZ) Örgütsel Bağlılık (ÖB) üzerindeki etkisini incelemek, ikinci amacı ise bu ilişkide İş Tatmininin (İT) bir aracı rolü olup olmadığını anlamaktır. Çalışma Ürdün'de farklı üretim firmalarından elde edilen verilerle yürütülmüştür. Örneklemi 411 çalışan oluşturmaktadır. Araştırma, DZ, İT ve ÖB ölçmek için güvenilirlik ve geçerli kabul görmüş ölçekler kullanılarak nicel bir yöntemle yürütülmüştür. Elde edilen verilere, SPSS programı kullanılarak normallik testleri, betimleyici istatistikler, korelasyon ve regresyon analizi yapılmıştır. Buna ilave olarak SPSS PROCESS Makro uygulaması da kullanılarak aracılık testi bulguları doğrulanmıştır. Bulgulara göre, DZ hem İT hem de ÖB üzerinde önemli ve olumlu bir etkiye sahiptir. İT'nin, DZ ve ÖB arasındaki ilişkiye kısmen aracılık ettiği bulunmuştur. Bu bulgu, DZ'nin ÖB üzerindeki olumlu etkisinin artan İT aracılığıyla gerçekleştiğini göstermektedir. Bu sonuç yüksek DZ'ya sahip çalışanların daha yüksek İT deneyimlediğini ve bunun da kuruluşa olan bağlılıklarını güçlendirdiğini göstermektedir. Çalışma, DZ ve İT'nin ÖB teşvik etmedeki önemini desteklemekte ve alan yazınına ampirik kanıtlar sağlayarak katkıda bulunmaktadır. Sonuçlar, üretici firmalara çalışanların DZ'sını geliştirmeleri ve İT'ni artırabilecek işyeri politikaları geliştirmeleri gerektiğini vurgulamaktadır. Böylelikle şirketler daha bağlılık sahibi bir iş gücü yetiştirebilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Duygusal Zekâ, İş Tatmini, Örgütsel Bağlılık, Aracılık Analizi, İmalat Sektörü.

Introduction

Today, the Organizational Commitment (OC) of employees plays a valuable role in determining the success of their organizations (Cesário and Chambel, 2017). OC functions as a vital part of the well-being of an organization and affects the retention of employees and their alignment with the goals of the companies. Therefore, it is essential to understand the factors that lead to or hinder OC in order to cultivate a motivated and committed workforce in contemporary companies. The term OC refers to the willingness and desire of members of an organization to work towards the goals of the organization (Yandi and Havidz, 2022). Rahiman et al. (2020) emphasize the importance of OC as a high OC corresponds to improved job performance, increased employee loyalty, and lower turnover. For example, employees with high Emotional Intelligence (EI) may exhibit stronger OC due to their ability to productively overcome workplace challenges (Miao et al., 2017). While these insights highlight the importance of OC, there are still gaps in the literature, especially in terms of its mediators and context-specific effects (Elayan et al., 2023). OC is an individual's ability to control and manage overwhelming emotions and aims to transform these emotions into a helping tool that enables employees to effectively cope with workplace challenges and build strong

relationships, which significantly increases their OC (Alzoubi et al., 2021). The term Job Satisfaction (JS), on the other hand, refers to a set of emotions used to determine whether the job or task is pleasant for the employee at work, and this satisfaction plays an important role in fostering OC by increasing the emotional bond and loyalty of the staff to the organization (Afolashade et al., 2024). This interconnectedness between JS and OC highlights the importance of investigating these variables in specific organizational settings. An outstanding example of this is the manufacturing sector in Jordan, which is considered a critical component of the Jordanian economy (Al-Hyari et al., 2011). Despite this and its importance, this area has not been sufficiently explored in this context, leading to the perception that there is a lack of studies addressing how EI affects OC through JS in this particular sector. This leaves a significant gap in understanding the dynamics of the Jordanian manufacturing sector and their impact on employee commitment. In order to fill this gap, the aim of this research was to conduct an investigation into the function of the mediating variable JS in the link between EI and OC in the manufacturing sector of Jordan. While EI and JS are well-known elements in workplace dynamics, their combined impact on OC, especially in the manufacturing sector in Jordan, has not yet been examined. Focused on the context, the current research will provide actionable insights for policy makers and managers in the manufacturing sector of Jordan, which will in turn support them in knowing how to increase employee satisfaction and commitment. This research will attempt to fill this gap by explaining how EI affects OC through JS, and will provide important insights into the factors that promote employee commitment.

Literature Review

In this part of the study, firstly, theoretical information about organizational commitment, then emotional intelligence and job satisfaction variables will be conveyed.

Organizational Commitment

OC is often considered as one of the key concepts researched in making sense of employee behavior in organizations. Employees with higher levels of commitment are more likely to engage in non-discretionary behaviors that increase workplace productivity, while those with lower commitment are at a higher risk of employee turnover (Rastogi, 2013). Various studies have highlighted the importance of OC in developing a stable and engaged workforce, especially in industries that require long-term employee commitment, such as manufacturing, healthcare, and education (Mehra, 2023). Therefore, understanding OC not only helps organizations improve employee engagement but also provides insights into workforce motivation (Rahmatullah et al., 2022). For example, studies such as Cesário and Chambel (2017) found that higher degrees of OC are associated with increased job performance and lower absenteeism. DiPietro et al. (2020) noted that employees who feel responsible towards their organization are more likely to demonstrate higher commitment, stronger teamwork, and a proactive approach to problem solving. In addition, organizations with engaged employees experience lower turnover rates, which is especially critical in industries such as manufacturing, where a high rate can disrupt production processes and increase operational costs (Luthfi et al., 2022).

Another study conducted by Herrera and De Las Heras-Rosas (2021) found that companies with higher levels of OC exhibit stronger innovation capabilities and overall better organizational performance, indicating the long-term benefits of fostering commitment among employees. OC is a multidimensional construct, typically comprising three dimensions: affective commitment (AC), continuance commitment (CC), and normative commitment (NC) (Meyer & Allen, 1997). AC is considered the most desirable form of commitment as it reflects and takes into account an employee's commitment to their organization (Onukwu et al., 2020). Employees with high AC stay with their organization because they want to rather than out of obligation (Meyer and Allen, 1997). CC is based on the evaluation of employees in terms of the costs associated with leaving their current organization as well as the withdrawal from their current organization (Muthuveloo and Rose, 2005; Kuhal et al., 2020). DiPietro et al., (2020) stated that employees with high CC may stay with their organization not because of emotional attachment but because they perceive significant financial, social, or career-related losses if they leave. This type of commitment is often influenced by multiple components including tenure, salary, benefits, and labor market conditions (Luthfi et al., 2022). The NC dimension considers an employee's sense of duty and moral obligation to stay with their organization (Harini and Utami, 2020). Employees with high NC often feel that withdrawing from the organization would be disloyal or unethical due to cultural influences, company values, or personal beliefs (Meyer and Allen, 1997). All three dimensions—AC, CC, and NC—are important, and each dimension affects employee motivation in different ways (Meyer and Allen, 1997). In this study, AC, CC, and NC were measured using Meyer and Allen's (1997) OC Scale, a widely validated and reliable instrument. A detailed description of the scale is provided in the Methodology section. Although previous studies have examined OC in a variety of industries, there is a gap in understanding how OC operates in the Jordanian manufacturing sector, particularly in relation to EI and JS.

Emotional Intelligence

The concept of EI can be characterized as having the capacity and ability to observe and recognize one's own and others' emotions and feelings (Salovey and Mayer, 1990). EI offers an individual the ability to improve work performance, includes positive roles it will bring to organizations such as leading to productivity and better collaboration with others, and is therefore vital in the workplace (Oliver, 2020; Sembiring et al., 2020; Giao et al., 2020). According to Bradberry (2023), employees who develop strong EI skills can effectively cope with workplace challenges such as resolving conflicts and adapting to challenging situations. Today, many organizations accept EI as an important component in departments such as recruitment, training, and leadership development programs (Lopes, 2016). Employees with high EI demonstrate strong adaptability to change, superior conflict resolution skills, and higher levels of resilience in challenging work environments (Oliver, 2020). Sembiring et al. (2020) stated that employees with high emotional intelligence will be more likely to engage in positive workplace interactions, leading to better communication and fewer misunderstandings. Additionally, employees with high EI are better at grasping the emotional

needs of others, coping with stress, and contributing to a constructive work culture (Ozoekwe and Konya, 2021).

Individuals with high emotional intelligence are more empathetic and can communicate more effectively, deal with conflicts, and contribute to a productive work environment (Giao et al., 2020). Sharma et al. (2024) report that employees with high EI are significantly better at resolving conflicts, maintaining motivation, and strengthening teamwork. These findings suggest that EI is a determining factor in maintaining productivity and stability in organizations. Bradberry (2023) noted that employees with high levels of EI are more adaptable and effective in teamwork, with stronger problem-solving skills. Employees with high emotional intelligence are thought to be better at interpreting social cues and handling disagreements diplomatically, and to maintain a balanced perspective on work-related challenges (Afolashade et al., 2024). EI is also suggested to play a significant role when it comes to enhancing OC, as staff members with high EI will emotionally invest a lot in their organization, resulting in greater loyalty, less turnover, and a stronger attachment to their workplace (Miao et al., 2017). An additional factor linking EI to OC is emotional self-regulation, as employees who effectively manage their emotions are better at coping with work-related stress and maintaining motivation even in challenging situations (Giao et al., 2020). In addition, EI can promote alignment between employees' personal goals and the organization's mission, making them feel more committed to the company's goals (Kuhail et al., 2020). This alignment can increase the likelihood of employees committing to their organization in the long term. It will be noticed that EI serves as a driving force in maintaining organizational stability, as employees with high emotional intelligence have an extra dedication towards their work environment (Extremera et al., 2018). The positive impact of EI on OC highlights the importance of promoting emotional awareness and interpersonal skills within organizations to support long-term employee retention and engagement. Giao et al., (2020) found that staff with a reasonable degree of EI showed greater satisfaction with their work environment because they were able to successfully communicate their needs and strengthen collaborative workplace connections. This suggests that EI is an important element in improving workplace morale and overall JS.

Job Satisfaction

Marques et al. (2018) define JS as a state of positive emotions derived from an employee's job and its multiple aspects. JS has been widely studied in organizational psychology and human resource management, with the idea that employees feel well-being at work and thus an important determinant of workplace productivity (Judge et al., 2020). It is believed that employees who experience high levels of JS will tend to be more engaged, motivated, and productive, which will directly impact on organizations' outcomes such as productivity, retention, and overall efficiency (Memon et al., 2023). Thant and Chang's (2021) study highlights that JS has an impact on multiple elements such as working conditions, relationships with coworkers, compensation, and individual mental characteristics. Studies such as the study by Karanika-Murray et al. (2015) have shown that employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to exhibit strong workplace commitment, lower absenteeism, and higher levels of organizational involvement. JS is considered an important factor

in workplace success as it positively impacts employee performance, OC, and overall productivity (Katebi et al., 2022). A study conducted by Badrianto and Ekhsan (2020) in the manufacturing sector of Japan found that JS has a direct impact on employee productivity. Their findings are in line with the findings of Suifan (2019) who stated that JS leads to higher employee loyalty and a stronger sense of belonging within an organization, which reduces the risks associated with high turnover. Employees who feel that their efforts at work are valued and recognized are more likely to experience JS (Arian et al., 2018).

Having the potential to make decisions and feeling autonomous also positively influences JS (Andreas, 2022). Opportunities for career advancement and skill development contribute to higher levels of satisfaction (Kang & Malvaso, 2023). Employees who have more control over their work and are repeatedly recognized for their contributions exhibit stronger JS. According to Hudays et al. (2024), employees who are given professional development opportunities have significantly higher levels of satisfaction compared to those who are not. If the company culture is a positive and inclusive workplace culture, it may encourage higher JS (Bektaş, 2017). Compensation and benefits are also strong influencers; fair salaries, bonuses, and benefits significantly affect employee satisfaction levels (Suifan, 2019). Employees who experience security in their jobs tend to be more satisfied with their jobs and are significantly less likely to seek alternative employment (Thant & Chang, 2021). Wieneke et al. (2019) study found that flexibility, fair wages, and strong leadership in the workplace contribute significantly to JS. It is expected that employees who can balance work and personal life will tend to have higher levels of satisfaction (Topino et al., 2021). Family responsibilities also play a role; employees with a family support structure experience less stress and more satisfaction (Hudays et al., 2024). In addition, psychological and physical health directly affects an employee's attitude towards work, as higher well-being will provide an additional positive workplace experience (Thant and Chang, 2021). This highlights the importance of supportive workplace policies that enable staff to balance work and personal responsibilities.

Winton (2023) emphasizes a strong link between JS and OC variables. For example, workforce members who are satisfied with their employment positions are likely to foster a sense of commitment and loyalty to their workplace and increase overall engagement. Al-Refaei et al. (2023) study found that higher JS leads to stronger AC, meaning employees are more emotionally attached to their workplace. Employees who feel valued and appreciated develop stronger bonds with their organizations, leading to lower absenteeism rates and higher retention (Martin and Uribe, 2021). Employees who feel financially stable and have secure career prospects in their organization are less likely to seek external job opportunities with high job satisfaction (Jufrizen et al., 2023).

Studies in the field reinforce the idea that improving JS can serve as a tactical tool for organizations to improve workforce engagement and reduce turnover rates. Renukaradhya and Pinapati (2024) describes JS as a fundamental aspect of workplace dynamics, affecting employee engagement, OC, and overall job performance. Despite extensive research on JS, more studies are needed to explore the mediating role between EI and OC, especially in industry-specific contexts such as manufacturing. By labeling this gap, the aim of this research is to provide an actionable

understanding along with awareness for organizations that aim to increase long-term commitment and employee satisfaction.

Relationships Between Variables and Hypotheses Development

EI plays an important role in shaping employees' attitudes toward their organizations. Employees with high EI are preferred in managing their emotions, adapting to workplace challenges, and establishing strong interpersonal relationships, which directly contribute to workplace commitment (Miao et al., 2017). EI improves employees' ability to regulate stress and maintain motivation, leading to a stronger emotional bond with their workplace (Extremera et al., 2018). Rahman et al. (2021) state that employees with high EI show increased levels of emotional commitment as they align more closely with organizational goals and values. Furthermore, employees with high emotional intelligence tend to create positive work environments, reduce turnover intentions, and strengthen their long-term commitment to their organizations (Goleman, 1995). Hypothesis-1 was developed based on these studies:

H1: Emotional intelligence positively affects organizational commitment.

The relationship between EI and JS is well established in organizational behavior studies. Employees with higher levels of EI will be more capable of managing stress, resolving conflicts, and maintaining positive workplace relationships, all of which contribute to a greater sense of JS (Sembiring et al., 2020). Individuals who are able to recognize as well as regulate their emotions tend to have more optimistic attitudes toward their jobs, resulting in higher engagement and motivation (Giao et al., 2020). The same study suggests that employees with higher emotional intelligence are better at coping with workplace challenges, leading to lower levels of frustration as well as burnout. Employees with higher EI also tend to perceive their working conditions as more supportive. As a result, this leads to increased scores in JS (Bradberry, 2023). Based on these studies, Hypothesis-2 was developed:

H2: Emotional intelligence positively affects job satisfaction.

Employees who are satisfied with their jobs are more likely to develop a strong commitment to their workplace, which plays a role in increasing commitment ratings (Winton, 2023). Higher levels of JS support a sense of Commitment and make employees more willing to contribute to organizational goals (Jufrizen et al., 2023). Studies show that satisfied employees are less likely to withdraw from their organizations and more likely to engage in non-mandatory behaviors that support the organization's success (Martin & Uribe, 2021). Furthermore, employees who perceive their jobs as fulfilling and rewarding exhibit higher levels of commitment, reinforcing the idea that JS directly affects OC (Al-Refaei et al., 2023). Hypothesis-3 was developed in relation to these studies:

H3: Job satisfaction positively affects organizational commitment.

Güteryüz et al. (2008) found that JS plays a significant role in linking EI to OC, as employees with high emotional intelligence experience higher JS. Therefore, this concept will strengthen employees' commitment and loyalty to the organization (Giao et al., 2020; Soriano-Vázquez et al.,

2023). Although studies such as Güleriyüz et al. (2008) have investigated this mediating role, research on this relationship remains limited, especially in the context of the Jordanian manufacturing sector. Most of the existing studies have focused on service sectors such as healthcare and banking. There is a gap in understanding how JS mediates EI and OC in manufacturing-based work environments. Since manufacturing jobs often have unique workplace conditions and job expectations, it is essential to examine this relationship in this context. Based on these studies, Hypothesis-4 was developed:

H4: Job satisfaction mediates the relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational commitment.

Methodology

The Research Model presented in Figure 1 was prepared in order to test the hypotheses developed with the information and theoretical support presented in the literature review section of the research.

Figure 1. Research Model

Sampling

Convenience sampling was used for this study. This is because the method is inexpensive, effective, and easy to implement. This method is suitable for collecting data from employees in the manufacturing sector in Jordan because it provides easy access to participants, but it does not guarantee full representation of the population (Jager et al., 2017). The survey instrument in this study consisted of a total of 41 items and the minimum sample size required was calculated as 410 participants (41 items \times 10). This formula was used based on the suggestion of Hair et al. (2014) for the adequacy of the sample size and to guarantee statistical reliability. Accordingly, the data sample should not be less than ten times the number of items used in the scale. Feedback was obtained from a total of 411 employees working in the manufacturing sector in Jordan using Google Forms as the data collection tool. All responses were usable since the survey design prevented participants from skipping questions and ensured that there was no missing or incorrect data. Therefore, Hair et al. (2014) guideline, the final sample size of 411 participants exceeds the minimum requirement of 410, indicating the statistical adequacy of the sample. Although convenience sampling was used due to its cost-effectiveness and accessibility, the sample size and

diversity ensure that the findings adequately represent the target population in the Jordanian manufacturing sector.

In this study, the necessary ethical approval for the implementation of the survey was received from Istanbul Aydin University Social and Human Sciences Ethics Committee. Report Date: 20.02.2025. Report Number: 2025/02.

Measurement Tools Used in the Research

Data were collected using a demographic information form and three different scales. The scales are in 5-point Likert style and have options such as agree or disagree.

Organizational Commitment Scale

The Organizational Commitment Scale was developed by Allen and Meyer (1990). The scale has 3 factors and consists of 24 items. Sub-dimensions are: Affective Commitment, Continuity Commitment and Normative Commitment and the scale's unidimensional Cronbach's alpha score is 0.70. In current study, the scale was included in the analyses as unidimensional. In the current study, the KMO value of the scale was found as 0.918 and the Cronbach Alpha Value was found as 0.853.

Emotional Intelligence Scale

The Brief Emotional Intelligence Scale (BEIS-10) —Revised, developed by Davies et al. (2010), was used in this study. Individuals' perceptions of their own emotional intelligence are measured. The BEIS-10 Scale consists of 10 items and 5 factors. The sub-dimensions are: appraisal of own emotions, appraisal of others' emotions, regulation of own emotions, regulation of others' emotions, and utilization of emotions. The scale has a Cronbach's alpha coefficient equal to 0.86 in its unidimensional form, and was included in the analyses in the current study with its unidimensional structure. In the present search, the KMO value of the scale was found as 0.810 and the Cronbach Alpha Value was found as .0.726.

Job Satisfaction Scale

The Brief Affective Job Satisfaction Index (BIAJS) developed by Thompson and Phua (2012) was used. The Scale consists of 7 items as 1 factor. The values of the original Scale, BIAJS, showed good internal consistency reliability with a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.84, indicating that the BIAJS is a reliable tool for measuring JS in various populations. In the current study, the KMO value of the scale was found as 0.776 and the Cronbach Alpha Value was found as 0.741.

Findings

The data set obtained from the employees was tested with the Social Sciences Statistical Package (SPSS) 30.0 program. The analysis includes demographic characteristics, descriptive statistics, internal consistency reliability, normality tests, analysis of the correlation, regression analysis, as well as mediation analysis.

Descriptive Statistics

The demographic information of the participants is presented in Table 1, with frequency and percentage values prepared in an effort to provide descriptive information about the research sample. It can be said that the majority of the research sample consists of male, 18-34 age group, bachelor's degree graduates, entry-level employees with 1-10 years of working experience.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	Demographics	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	219	53.3
	Female	192	46.7
Age	18–24 years	105	25.5
	25–34 years	179	34.6
	35–44 years	93	22.6
	45 + years	34	8.3
	High school diploma	58	14.1
Educational Level	Bachelor	268	65.2
	Master	66	16.1
	Doctorate	19	4.6
Years of Work Experience	Less than 5 years	138	33.6
	5–10 years	165	40.1
	More than 10 years	108	26.3
Job Level/Position	Entry-Level	183	44.5
	Mid-Level	178	43.3
	Senior/Executive-Level	50	12.2

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Internal consistency and normality distributions of variables are presented with means, standard deviations, skewness and kurtosis scores regarding the study variables are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Internal consistency and normality distribution results

	EI	JS	OC
Mean	29.8465	19.8408	71.2493
Std. Deviation	5.81408	3.72428	7.42123
Skewness	.178	.053	.012
Kurtosis	.115	.418	7.852
Cronbach Alpha (α)	.726	.741	.853

Reliability analyses showed that Cronbach's alpha values for EI, JS, and OC were 0.726, 0.741, and 0.853, respectively. According to Nunnally (1978), Cronbach's alpha values above 0.70 are acceptable. It indicates that the scales used in this study have acceptable to high internal consistency. This indicates that the measurement tools are reliable for assessing the constructs of EI, JS, and OC.

In addition, skewness and kurtosis analysis values were reviewed to assess the normality of the data distribution. Skewness values ranged from 0.012 to 0.178, while kurtosis values ranged from 0.115 to 7.852. According to Field (2018), skewness values between -2 and +2 and kurtosis values between -7 and +7 are generally considered acceptable to assume normality in the data distribution. Moreover, the test result values in Table 2 confirm that the data distribution is acceptable for parametric statistical analyses such as regression and mediation analysis. It is understood that the kurtosis value for OC is slightly outside the acceptable limit and forms a peak.

The mean scores for EI, JS, and OC are 2.98, 2.83, and 2.97, respectively, indicating the average levels of these constructs among the participants. The standard deviations for EI, JS, and OC are 1.84, 1.41, and 1.51, respectively, reflecting the variability of the responses around the mean. These values indicate that the participants' scores are relatively consistent and moderately distributed around the mean for each variable.

Correlation Test

A Pearson correlation analysis was applied to examine the relationships between EI, OC and JS. The correlation provides insight into the direction and strength of the relationships between these elements. A positive correlation gives a signal that as one variable increases, the other variable also increases, while a negative correlation indicates the opposite relationship. The results of the correlation matrix is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variable	EI	OC	JS
EI	1		
OC	.545**	1	
JS	.617**	.563**	1

** p<0.01

The results of the analysis show that all correlations are statistically significant. A moderate positive correlation was found between EI and OC, indicating that higher EI is associated with higher OC. A moderate to strong positive correlation was found between EI and JS, indicating that personnel with higher EI tend to experience greater JS. A moderate positive correlation was found between JS and OC, indicating that JS is positively associated with OC. These findings are in line with the expectations of the research hypotheses.

Regression Tests

In the first step, linear regression research was conducted to examine both the direction and strength of the link between EI and OC. This analysis can estimate how much of the changes in OC can be attributed to changes in EI. The regression coefficient (B) represents the extent to which EI affects

OC. When there is a statistically significant t value, it further confirms the reliability of the estimated result. Table 4 presents the regression coefficients for this model.

Table 4: Regression Coefficients: EI on OC

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	50.505	1.610		31.377	<0.001
EI	.695	.053	.545	13.129	<0.001

In the regression test conducted to investigate the effect of EI on OC, the model was found to be statistically significant [F (1,409) = 172.37, p<.001]. The model can explain 29.6% of the variance in OC ($R^2=.296$). (B=0.695, t=13.13, p<.001). This finding shows that higher EI leads to stronger OC (Alsughayir, 2021; Sodeinde, 2024). The findings of this regression analysis show that Hypothesis-1 is supported.

In the second step, linear regression analysis was conducted to examine how EI affects JS. The values obtained from the regression analysis are reported in Table 5. The results show the extent to which EI affects JS and whether this relationship is statistically significant.

Table 5: Regression Coefficients: EI on JS

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	5.458	.970		5.630	<0.001
EI	.521	.032	.629	16.344	<0.001

As a result of linear regression analysis conducted to examine the effect of EI on JS, the model was found to be statistically significant [F(1, 409) =267.12, p<.001]. The second model was found to explain 39.4% of the variance in JS ($R^2=.394$). A strong positive effect of EI on JS was determined (B=0.521, t=16.34, p<.001), indicating that higher EI significantly increased JS. According to the findings of this regression analysis, Hypothesis-2 is supported.

In the third step, linear regression analysis was also performed to evaluate the effect of JS on OC. The regression analysis values are given in Table 6.

Table 4: Regression Coefficients: JS on OC

Predictor	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	53.316	1.366		39.038	<0.001
JS	.853	.063	.554	13.471	<0.001

The model was found to be statistically significant [F(1,409) =181.47, p<.001]. The model can explain 30.7% of the variance in OC ($R^2=.307$). JS has a moderate positive effect on OC (B=0.853,

$t=13.47$, $p<.001$), indicating that higher JS leads to stronger OC. Based on this finding, it can be said that Hypothesis-3 is supported.

In the 4th step, the PROCESS Macro test suggested by Hayes (2018) was conducted to investigate the mediation role. The mediation analysis will determine whether the independent variable EI has an indirect effect on the dependent variable OC through the mediator JS. According to Hayes (2018), the mediation role should include confidence intervals that do not include zero, and after this check, the mediation role is confirmed when the indirect effect is statistically significant. Table 7 shows both the direct and indirect effects of EI on OC through JS.

Table 7: Regression Analysis for Direct and Indirect Effects

Predictor	B	SE	t	p	95% CI (LL)	95% CI (UL)
DV: JS						
EI	.5211	.0319	16.34	<.001	.4585	.5838
DV: OC						
EI	.4137	.0644	6.42	<.001	.2870	.5404
JS	.5399	.0777	6.95	<.001	.3871	.6927
Indirect Effect (Mediation via JS)	.2813	.0527	-	-	.1783	.3856

B = Unstandardized Coefficients; SE = Standard Error; LLCI = Lower Limit Confidence Interval; ULCI = Upper Limit Confidence Interval.

In the analysis, Model 4 representing the research model was used among the models included in PROCESS Macro. 95% confidence level and 5,000 bootstraps were applied in the test. It is also possible to evaluate all hypotheses at this testing stage. The findings show that EI has a significant direct effect on OC ($\beta=.4137$, $p<.001$, 95% CI [.2870, .5404]), while also indicating that Hypothesis-1 is supported. From the same findings, EI significantly predicts JS ($\beta=.5211$, $p<.001$, 95% CI [.4585, .5838]), thus confirming that Hypothesis-2 is also supported. JS significantly affects OC ($\beta=.5399$, $p<.001$, 95% CI [.3871, .6927]), supporting Hypothesis 3. The bootstrapped indirect effect of EI on OC via JS was found to be significant ($\beta=.2813$, $\text{BootSE}=.0527$, 95% CI [.1783, .3856]). In this case, since the two confidence intervals do not include the number zero, this confirms the mediating role of JS in the relationship between EI and OC, supporting H4.

The regression model predicting JS from EI explained 39.5% of the difference ($R^2=.3951$, $p<.001$), indicating a strong estimated relationship. Similarly, the model predicting OC from EI and JS explained 37.1% of the variance ($R^2=.3709$, $p<.001$). The results show that JS partially mediates the relationship between EI and OC. This suggests that higher EI strengthens JS, which in turn strengthens OC, but EI also has an independent effect on OC that is not explained by JS. This finding is consistent with the work of Baron and Kenny (1986) who argued that partial mediation occurs when the independent variable continues to have a significant direct effect on the dependent variable after accounting for the mediator. Similarly, Hayes (2022) and Zhao et al. (2010) emphasize that partial mediation is more common in social science research because most

relationships are influenced by more than one factor. The findings of this regression analysis show that Hypothesis-4 is supported.

Discussion

The findings are consistent with the EI theory of Salovey and Mayer (1990), which suggests that EI enhances individuals' ability to manage their emotions, build relationships, and overcome workplace challenges. The current study extends existing knowledge by showing that EI not only directly influences OC but also operates indirectly through JS. The findings are consistent with several studies examining the EI-JS-OC relationship. For example, Alsughayir (2021) study in the banking sector in Saudi Arabia found that EI significantly predicted both JS and OC, with JS acting as a partial mediator. This study, like ours, highlights the importance of EI in improving workplace attitudes and behaviors. However, some studies have reported different findings. For example, Gao et al. (2020) found that the mediating portion of JS was stronger in service sectors compared to manufacturing sectors, suggesting that industry-specific factors may influence these relationships. Additionally, Miao et al. (2017) observed that the direct effect of EI on OC is weaker in collectivist cultures, where organizational loyalty is often driven by normative commitment rather than emotional attachment.

The Jordanian context in the current study may have influenced the findings, as Jordan's collectivist culture, characterized by strong family ties and social harmony, may have increased the importance of EI in strengthening the workplace and commitment link. For example, employees with high EI may be better equipped to navigate the social dynamics of a collectivist workplace, leading to higher JS and OC. This is consistent with Hofstede's (1980) cultural dimensions theory, which suggests that collectivist cultures place greater emphasis on interpersonal harmony and group loyalty. However, there are also distinct challenges in Jordan, such as the manufacturing sector, high labor force, and limited career advancement opportunities. This may also make the EI-JS-OC link flexible. Specifically, JS plays a mediating role in this relationship, as EI influences OC through its influence on JS.

Conclusion

This study highlights the role of EI in creating JS and OC among employees in the Jordanian manufacturing sector. The findings reveal that EI significantly influences both JS and OC, indicating that employees with high emotional intelligence are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs and committed to their organizations. This is in line with previous studies such as Sodeinde (2024) that focus on recognizing the value of EI in improving workplace attitudes and behaviors. The study also highlights the mediating role of JS in the link between EI and OC, indicating that EI directly influences OC and indirectly through JS. The results suggest that organizations should prioritize initiatives aimed at developing EI among employees, as this not only increases their ability to manage emotions and cope with workplace challenges, but also supports a more positive and engaged workforce. Furthermore, EI training programs can help employees develop skills such as empathy and self-awareness, as well as emotional regulation, which are crucial for maintaining workplace harmony and productivity. Additionally, Organizations should focus on creating work

environments that encourage JS through fair compensation, recognition, career development golden opportunities, and supportive leadership.

In the Jordanian context, the collectivist nature of the culture may enhance the role of EI in fostering workplace connections as well as engagement. Employees with high EI are better equipped to navigate the social dynamics of a collectivist workplace, which may lead to higher JS and OC. However, the unique challenges of the manufacturing sector, such as high workload and limited career advancement opportunities, may moderate this relationship. Future research should examine these dynamics in more depth to uncover more nuanced insights.

Furthermore, the findings contribute to the broader field of workplace psychology by reinforcing the interconnectedness of EI, employee well-being, and organizational outcomes. As Lai, Gao and Du (2024) note, fostering a culture that promotes emotional awareness and satisfaction is crucial to retaining an organizational identification. Organizations that invest in EI and JS initiatives may experience long-term benefits such as higher employee retention, improved productivity, and enhanced organizational performance. These outcomes are exceptionally important in the manufacturing sector, where employee dedication is critical to maintaining operational efficiency and competitiveness.

Although the research emerged with perceptions that are considered valuable, it is not without limitations. This study was conducted within specific cultural and industrial contexts that may limit the generalizability of the study's discovery to other conditions. Future studies should investigate the EI-JS-OC relationship across industries and cultural contexts to validate and extend the current findings. Furthermore, the study focused on EI and JS as well as OC but did not account for other potential influencing aspects such as the organization's culture, leadership styles, or even job autonomy. Including these variables in future research could provide an additional comprehensive perception of the dynamics at play. In conclusion, this research emphasizes the value of EI and JS as key drivers of OC. By prioritizing EI evolution and creating working conditions that enhance JS, organizations can embed an extra loyal and engaged staff. As workplaces continue to face dynamic challenges, a strong emphasis on these elements will be important for maintaining workforce stability as well as performance. Future research should build on these findings to further develop best practices for organizations seeking to build a resilient and emotionally intelligent workforce.

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